

HUMAN CHARACTERISTICS OF THE MAIN HERO IN TIM VICARI'S „ ELEPHANT MAN”

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Abstract. This article is devoted to the study of the expression of the basic characteristics of *Elephant man*. The introductory part gives a brief overview of the author's work and discusses the impact of the „Elephant Man” story. Thus, the effect of the short story is interpreted. The literature review section describes the similarities and differences in the style of other writers, how they analyzed „Elephant Man” and what verses were used in his story. Each of them will be discussed separately, giving more details. In the analysis and discussion section fragments from the work are given and analyzed. In the summary section, all the information is summarized.

Key words: Picture, Elephant Man, shop, creature, thing, prison, letter, card, nurse, queen.

ЧЕЛОВЕЧЕСКИЕ КАЧЕСТВА ГЛАВНОГО ГЕРОЯ РОМАНА ТИМА ВИКАРИ «ЧЕЛОВЕК-СЛОН»

Аннотация. Данная статья посвящена изучению выраженности основных характеристик человека-Слона. Во вводной части дается краткий обзор творчества автора и обсуждается влияние истории «Человек-слон». Таким образом интерпретируется эффект новеллы. В разделе обзора литературы описываются сходства и различия в стиле других писателей, то, как они анализировали «Человека-слона» и какие стихи использовались в его рассказе. О каждом из них поговорим отдельно, дав более подробную информацию. В разделе анализа и обсуждения приводятся и анализируются фрагменты из произведения. В сводном разделе вся информация обобщается.

Ключевые слова: Картина, Человек-слон, лавка, существо, вещь, тюрьма, письмо, карта, кормилица, королева.

INTRODUCTION

Tim Vicari is an experienced teacher and writer who has written several stories for the Oxford Bookworms Library. Most of them are in the Thriller and Adventure series, such as „White Death”, or in the True Stories series, such as „Elephant Man”, such as „The Coldest Place on Earth”. The story of the race between Scott and Amundsen to the South Pole. He also published two long novels, „Blood in the Rose” and „The Cat and the Mouse”.

Tim Vicari has two children and raises dogs, cats and horses. He lives and works in York, North England.

Victorian period, the medical field was not as developed as it is today. Doctors did not know what caused Joseph Merrick to become so dizzy. A scene showing the lower and middle class on a busy street in 19th century London.

During the Victorian era, people were divided into upper, middle, and lower classes, with many moving to London to work in factories and more educated, with doctors, lawyers, and engineers in the middle class. the class people had money and time to spend their free time like reading literature and going to the theater, people were afraid and making fun of those who were different.

The little boys ran after Merrick and hit him , people were arrested by the police for fear of his ugliness.

LITERATURE REVIEW

„Elephant Man» is a short story that has been deeply studied and analyzed by David Lynch. It is dedicated to the life of John Merrick. He says: „ *Merrick, a man with severe deformities, was born in Victoria, England, during a period of heavy industrialization in which horrific demonstrations concealed the existence of a class society.*”

Joseph Merrick's ugly appearance frightened people and convinced people that he would hurt them. His physical imperfections really made him look like an elephant, so he explained the reason for the name: The elephant is human. However, Dr. Frederick Treves saw the outside of the skin and decided to give Merrick a lifetime chance that it would live and not be used. Later in the story, we learn that Merrick has a child-like character and that like other men, he loves to read books and was very happy when Treves friend Mrs. and Queen visited him. This means that a person should not be judged based on what he sees, because it is not the appearance that matters, but the interior itself. As well as Adam Augustyn said : „ *Joseph Merrick was famous because of his extreme physical deformities. His head was almost three feet in circumference, and spongy skin hung from his face and the back of his head. Deformation of the jaws prevented him from showing facial expression and speaking clearly. His right arm and both legs were similarly deformed.*”

In Tim Vicari's „Elephant Man” I find Dr. Frederick Treves's first encounter with the Elephant memorable, because it was through this experience that „Elephant Man” Joseph Merrick was able to live a good life. Dr. Treves first came across a poster depicting an elephant man near the hospital where he worked. Ashley Montagu says about this: „*Tim Vicaris Elephant Man caught my attention for many reasons. The plot of the story is closely related to the discrimination we are experiencing today. The unfortunate man, whose skin condition required medical attention, was humiliated for the ugliness of Joseph Merrick. Unfortunately, it was not only degraded, but also used by the shopkeeper as a source of income*”.

ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

The elephant man Merrick also reveals the developing Victorian English lifestyle. We find the shortcomings of this society in which different social classes and their vices are mixed. Yet violent swindlers or petty aristocrats use Merrick's appearance for useful, treacherous, and unhealthy purposes. John Merrick exposes their fraud with politeness and respect for the guests. With this confrontation, every encounter between Merrick and this community will be deeply impacting. The vices of this English society are contrary to the unspoken belief of the ‘circus freak’. „*Sometimes I think my head is too big because it's so full of dreams*”.

Another major highlight of the century is that Joseph Merrick is called a creature and a thing at the beginning of a work, but after his qualities, abilities, and interests are revealed throughout the work, he is also called a man : „ *I looked at the creature and felt sad . I am a doctor . I see horrible , ugly things every day . But this creature , this thing , was the worst of all . There were no men or women in the hospital like him.*”

Throughout the story of Tim Vicari's "Elephant Man," which I studied, I observed kindness in many of Dr. Frederick Treves' actions. Dr. Treves came across an ugly picture near the shop window near the hospital where he worked. Despite the ugly picture, Dr. Treves approached the elephant man in the picture and loved to watch him closely. „*Dr Treves, " he said, slowly. „You*

and the nurses are very kind, and I'm very happy here. Thank you very much. But. .. I know I can't stay here long, and . . . I would like to live in a lighthouse, after the hospital, please. A lighthouse, or a home for blind people. I think those are the best places for me."

Dr. Treves even offered more money to Joseph Merrick, the store clerk, to take Joseph Merrick, the store clerk, to the hospital to give the man a day off. The doctor was also kind enough to discuss Merrick's case with the hospital chairman, which resulted in a letter published in The Times and funds to allow the hospital to keep Merrick there. While Merrick was in the hospital, Dr. Treves wanted Merrick to feel at home and arranged for his girlfriend to visit Merrick. Despite people condemning Merrick, the doctor was never ashamed to go out with Merrick or make his dreams come true, and this time the doctor arranged for Merrick to visit the theater. It was because of Dr. Treves kindness to Merrick that his life changed for the better and happier, and if he hadn't had an accident in bed, Merrick would have lived a much happier life.

In Tim Vicari's book The Elephant Man, Carr Gomm played the role of a little hero, which had a positive effect on Joseph Merrick, the Elephant Man. Deaf Gomm was chairman of London Hospital. When Dr. Frederick Treves first introduced him to the elephant man, he decided to write a letter to The Times readers asking for financial help and keeping Merrick in the hospital life. *„ I am writing to you about a man in our hospital. He needs your help. His name is Joseph Merrick and he is 27 years old. He's not sick, but he can't get out of the hospital because he's so, so ugly. No one likes to look at him and some are afraid of him. We call him „Elephant Man”.*

This assistance and prompt action by the chairman resulted in funds that could be used for Merrick. However, Carr Gomm was also a responsible and honest man, as can be seen when he wrote another letter to The Times about Merrick's unfortunate death and the fact that the rest of the money intended for him would go to the hospital:

„The Times readers are very kind people. They gave us a lot of money. A week later, we had £ 50,000, so Merrick could live in the hospital for the rest of his life. We could have given him a home."

CONCLUSION

There is a purpose to writing any work. The main purpose of writing this work is to partially reveal the events of that period, not to judge a person by his appearance. In addition, compassion, which is the mainstay of the world, is to re-emphasize feelings such as consequences. Although Joseph Merrick lived a very short life, at the end of his life he felt a sense of compassion. He was also treated as a human being. He said many times at the end of his life that he was very pleased with the expansion of the ranks of his friends. Although he now felt a sense of happiness in the world, he was content with it. Even the fact that she had only a small picture of her mother who did not remember her was a small misfortune for her. Even so, he even met the queen and managed to be friend to her. He died feeling happy that way.

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